

A novel experimental setup for the stress test of geopolymer-based hydronic radiant panels using infrared thermography

by G. Ferrarini*, P. Bison*, A. Bortolin*, G. Cadelano*, M. Natali**, M. Panizza**, S. Tamburini**

* *Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto per le Tecnologie della Costruzione (CNR-ITC), Corso Stati Uniti 4, 35127, Padova, Italy, giovanni.ferrarini@itc.cnr.it*

** *Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto di Chimica per la Materia e di Tecnologie per l'Energia (CNR-ICMATE), Corso Stati Uniti 4, 35127, Padova, Italy*

Abstract

The European Project InnoWEE is developing radiant heating systems made with geopolymeric materials based on construction and demolition waste. For these systems, and in general for radiant systems, there are no standards or guidelines to assess the durability of the products as a whole. In a novel experimental setup, a prototype of radiant panel has been installed in a climatic chamber and thermally stressed cycling the water inlet temperature. Infrared thermography has been applied to check the thermal performance over time, verifying the stability after several days.

1. Introduction

The use of newly designed construction materials is a key strategy to increase the energy efficiency and the sustainability of buildings. In this framework, the Horizon 2020 European Project InnoWEE¹ (Innovative pre-fabricated components including different Waste Construction materials reducing building Energy consumption and minimising Environmental impacts) proposes the use of novel geopolymeric materials, based on construction and demolition wastes (CDW). Through the European Union, construction is indeed the economic activity with the major contribution to the production of waste². At the same time, buildings account for more than 40% of the energy consumption³. The InnoWEE projects aims to tackle both issues, using novel geopolymeric mixtures⁴ to build two types of façade panels and two types of radiant heating and cooling panels.

This work is focused on the radiant heating and cooling panels based on a high-density geopolymer mixture containing inorganic waste aggregates. The durability performance of a novel material or product is a critical issue during the development phase. Currently, there are no standards or guidelines to assess the durability of water based radiant panels as a whole. For this reason, a novel experimental setup was created to evaluate the radiant panels under thermal stress conditions, as described in the following section.

2. Materials and methods

Since several years, the CNR-ITC laboratories have a dedicated facility for the test of radiant heating and cooling panels, both water-based and electrical ones⁵. The experimental apparatus was extended after its creation and it can now test both small prototypes (inside a climatic chamber) and real scale installations, inside an industrial building. The climatic chamber that is used for prototype testing is an air jacket-type test room, with an internal volume of 130 m³, that includes a smaller room sizing 40 m³ and with dimensions based on the EN 14240⁶ specifications. The outer room is controlled by a dedicated air treatment unit that supplies hot or cold air through the jacket. Outside the room, a two-circuit hot and cold water generation system is installed.

For this work, the existing experimental setup was extended with the introduction of an automated water switching procedure. Both circuits were connected to the same feeding system in order to provide easily hot and cold water on a single circuit. A geopolymeric panel was installed in the thermal chamber and fed with a variable inlet temperature, cyclically alternating a pattern of hot and cold water (Figure 1) while the ambient was kept at a stable temperature.

Fig. 1: The water inlet to the panel is cycled between hot and cold. A full cycle lasts one hour.

The thermal response on the surface of the panels was recorded continuously with a thermal camera (FLIR SC660, spectral response 7.5µm - 13µm, NETD <30 mK, 640 x 480 pixel). The camera was set to capture a thermal image every 3 minutes.

3. Results

The panels were tested in different runs lasting up to 5 days, and the runs were repeated several times. The surface temperature of the panel in different times of the cycle is presented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Thermal images of the panel The water inlet to the panel is cycled between hot and cold.

The comparison of the recorded temperatures at different phases of the experiment showed that the performance of the panel remained stable after each cycle. This is confirmed also by the visual analysis of the surface of the panel.

4. Conclusions and perspectives

The proposed procedure, based on infrared thermography, could be applied easily to different types of water-based radiant panels. With some simplification, the setup could be integrated to the existing non-destructive quality controls during the production of radiant panels. A more detailed evaluation of the water inlet cycle parameters could be performed to evaluate the optimal conditions to thermally stress the panels.

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